

A

B

C

Supplementary Figure 2. A) Enzymatic fingerprinting of hemicellulose upon the mock treatment; the mutant *exo70B* lines have slightly more of acetylated hemicellulose. B) Enzymatic fingerprinting of hemicellulose upon the chitosan treatment; similarly to mock treatment, the *exo70B* mutant lines have more of acetylated hemicellulose. C) Comparison of hemicellulose composition of mock- and chitosan-treated plants for each line. Oligosaccharide nomenclature follows (Fry et al., 1993): G - glucose; X - xylose-glucose; L - galactose-xylose-glucose; F - fucose-galactose-xylose-glucose; Y - galacturonic acid-xylose-glucose; Ac: acetyl ester group. Data represents mean \pm SD, n = 4, *p < 0.05, **p < 0.01, student's t-test.